

MetaPaRSeq: Towards an efficient workflow for FLASH Radiotherapy RNA-Seq analysis ^{*}

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Abstract. Radiotherapy is one of the major cancer treatment strategies. However, its efficacy is limited by the development of radioresistance and damage to normal tissues. Many efforts have been made to improve radiotherapy efficacy. Recently a novel modality of radiation delivery has emerged. FLASH radiotherapy (FLASH-RT) allows for radiation delivery at ultra-high dose rates, which are much higher than conventional radiotherapy (CONV-RT). Studies have demonstrated a potential protective role of FLASH-RT in normal tissues, despite maintaining levels of tumor control at least equivalent to those of CONV-RT. Still, the mechanisms of FLASH-RT are not fully elucidated. This work aims to explore FLASH-RT by examining gene expression patterns and performing gene set enrichment analysis. This will be done through the use of MetaPaRSeq, a novel RNA-Seq data analysis workflow using High-Performance Computing (HPC) techniques. This research could provide a better comprehension of FLASH-RT biological mechanisms by uncovering its differential gene expression and activated pathways. FLASH-RT may become one of the main radiotherapy technologies in clinical practice in the future, being a promising new area of study.

Keywords: FLASH Radiotherapy · RNA-Seq · High-Performance Computing · Differential Expression Analysis · Gene Set Enrichment Analysis

1 Introduction

Cancer is considered one of the most complex and fatal diseases worldwide. New approaches to developing novel treatment strategies are relevant subjects of research [1]. Radiotherapy is one of the major cancer treatment strategies. However, its efficacy is limited by the development of radioresistance and damage to normal tissues. Many efforts have been made to improve radiotherapy efficacy [8]. Recently a novel modality of radiation delivery has emerged. FLASH radiotherapy (FLASH-RT) allows for radiation delivery at ultra-high dose rates, which are much higher than conventional radiotherapy (CONV-RT). Studies

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have demonstrated a potential protective role of FLASH-RT in normal tissues, despite maintaining levels of tumor control at least equivalent to those of CONV-RT [10]. Still, the mechanisms of FLASH-RT are not fully elucidated.

Transcriptomic studies can contribute to the understanding of the FLASH Radiotherapy’s effects. Transcriptomic data analysis can be used to identify genes that are differentially expressed in tissues that have been exposed to flash radiotherapy compared to tissues that have not been exposed to it. This can help identify the genes that are involved in the effects of flash radiotherapy. This type of study can also be used to uncover more about the pathways activated by this treatment strategy. Among the transcriptomic techniques, RNA-Seq analysis is a state-of-the-art technique used to measure the expression levels of genes in a cell or tissue [3].

An effective approach for analyzing RNA-Seq data is through the use of workflows, which may treat large volumes of data. Such an approach can be computationally intensive and require the use of high-performance computing (HPC) systems to guarantee an efficient analysis [4, 5].

This work aims to further understand the effects of FLASH Radiotherapy, focusing on the differential expression genes and activated pathways related, by exploring and analyzing RNA-Seq data. This will be performed via the use of a novel transcriptomics workflow modeled with bioinformatics HPC workflow managers and environments, which provides an efficient data analysis [4, 5].

2 Methodology

2.1 FLASH Radiotherapy Data

For the study of FLASH Radiotherapy and its effects, a paired-end run RNA-Seq dataset was chosen and retrieved from the Gene Expression Omnibus database (GEO Accession GSE173944), collected by Velalopoulou, Anastasia et al. [7]. Such data were obtained by performing transcriptional profiling (RNA-Seq) in skin and bone tissues from a mouse sarcoma model (*MusMusculus*).

The data can be organized as seen in Figure 1, where there are 2 tissues from where the data was collected: Bone and Skin. For both tissues, there are 3 condition groups consisting of untreated (Control), treated with standard radiation (Standard), and treated with FLASH Radiation (FLASH). For each of the condition groups, were collected 4 samples, consisting of 2 files for each sample, since the data is paired-end.

The data consists of 24 samples and 48 FASTQ files of about 13GB each, comprising a total of 624 GB of input. Such a high amount of data requires a powerful computational infrastructure and architecture. The use of a workflow developed to work with activities in parallel through the use of HPC techniques provides efficient management of those data.

2.2 Workflow

To deal with the Radiotherapy data selected, we propose the MetaParSeq workflow, which is based on the ParslRNA-Seq workflow for biological data analysis.

Fig. 1. Organization of FLASH Radiotherapy Data

ParslRNA-Seq [5] is a workflow for analyzing RNA-Seq experiments, which efficiently estimates the differential gene expression levels from raw sequencing reads and can be executed in varied computational environments, from personal computers to high-performance computing environments with parallel scripting library Parsl [4, 5]. Such workflow was developed by researchers from the National Laboratory of Scientific Computing (LNCC) and coupled to the Santos Dumont supercomputer from the Brazilian Supercomputer Center. This workflow was published in the journal *Communications in Computer and Information Science* in 2022 and was shown to be a good choice for the analysis of RNA-seq data from a variety of sources [4, 5].

A workflow for RNA-Seq analysis involves mainly: aligning the RNA-Seq reads to a reference genome, counting the number of reads that align to each gene in a reference genome, and performing differential expression analysis [12]. However, the ParslRNA-Seq workflow can be divided into 6 steps, as seen in Figure 2: Bowtie, Sort, Split, HTSeq, Merge and DESeq. Among those 6, there are 3 main activities: Bowtie, HTSeq, and DESeq, which are usually used in RNA-Seq data analysis to align the reads to a reference genome, count the number of reads that align to each gene in a reference genome and perform differential expression analysis, respectively. The remaining 3 steps (sort, split, and merge) are used to improve the performance of the workflow through its parallelization by sorting the reads by their genomic location, splitting the reads into smaller files, and merging those files back into a single file.

The difference between ParslRNA-Seq and the novel workflow, called MetaPaRSeq, proposed in this paper can be seen in Figure 4. MetaPaRSeq has the workflow ParslRNA-Seq as its base, however, contributes by adding an activity of gene enrichment analysis to uncover the metabolic pathways activated and related to FLASH Radiotherapy. Furthermore, it includes steps of quality control and adapts the activities for a high amount of paired-end cancer data.

This proposed workflow was adapted to deal with paired-end data instead of single-read (used in the ParslRNA-Seq workflow). The main difference between

Fig. 2. ParslRNA-Seq workflow view: (a) represents the steps of the workflow. (b) shows the activities executed in parallel.

paired-end FASTQ data and single-read FASTQ data is that paired-end data consists of two reads complementary to each other, while single-read data only consists of one read. An advantage of dealing with paired-end data is the improvement of the accuracy of read alignments [2]. An example of the paired-end data adaptation can be seen in the Bowtie activity in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Bowtie step. (a) Bowtie is used for single-read data. (b) Bowtie is used for paired-end data

While the ParslRNA-Seq workflow consists of 6 activities, MetaParSeq includes 4 more activities to obtain efficient and accurate results for differential expression analysis and gene set enrichment analysis. The proposed workflow starts with a quality control step through activities FastQC, Cutadapt, and MultiQC, which are popular tools for quality control of high-throughput sequencing data [13]. FastQC analyzes FASTQ files and generates a report of various qual-

ity metrics, such as sequence length distribution, per-base quality scores, and adapter content. Cutadapt trims adapter sequences and low-quality bases from FASTQ files. Finally, MultiQC is a graphical tool that combines the output of multiple quality control tools into a single report, providing a comprehensive overview of the quality of the data. This pre-processing step can be used to assess the quality of the sequencing runs and to identify any problems that need to be addressed before proceeding with the analysis [13].

After this step, MetaPaRSeq uses the pre-processed data and follows the workflow until it reaches the featureCounts activity. While the HTSeq tool can work with the paired-end FLASH data, because of the high amount of paired-end data, the featureCounts was chosen, since it is faster and more specialized for this type of data.

Finally, after the DESeq step, it is possible to analyze gene set enrichment and obtain more information about the biological pathways activated for each of the conditions studied (Control, Standard, and FLASH).

With the output of this workflow, it would be possible to get a better comprehension of the differences between such condition groups and understand the effects of FLASH Radiotherapy, a promising new area of research.

Fig. 4. ParslRNA-Seq versus MetaPaRSeq: (a) shows the steps of the ParslRNA-Seq workflow. (b) shows the steps of the MetaPaRSeq workflow.

3 Conclusions

The study of FLASH Radiotherapy is relevant and can bring changes in the way cancer is treated and how patients deal with this disease. The development of the proposed MetaPaRSeq workflow can bring to light more knowledge on how FLASH Radiotherapy works and its advantages over standard radiotherapy. MetaPaRSeq has been modeled and will be executed with the FLASH Radiotherapy data described in this paper. Also, large-scale tests will be performed on the Santos Dumont supercomputer from the Brazilian Supercomputer Center at LNCC. Such research will provide the scientific community with a novel workflow adapted for a high amount of paired-end data, including steps of quality

control and gene enrichment, that can be fast and carefully managed to provide insights into biological analysis.

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